

1 **Tumor suppressor inactivation results in PARP1 activation in osteosarcoma models in mice in vivo**
2 **and in human cells in vitro.**

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7 Parp1 exhibits anti-tumor activity in experiential models and is used for the treatment of multiple solid
8 tumor types. We described PARP1 as a therapeutic target and vulnerability in humans with lung cancer
9 (1), and provided evidence demonstrating that p53 status of the tumor rather than BRCA deficiency status
10 dictated PARP1 sensitivity in breast cancer (2). Here we describe here activation of PARP1 in
11 osteosarcoma. In osteosarcoma cells and in a genetically engineered tumor model of osteosarcoma
12 resulting from tumor suppressor inactivation, significant PARP1 induction was observed suggesting PARP
13 inhibition may possess therapeutic potential in clinical management of osteosarcoma, a childhood solid
14 tumor with limited treatment options.

15 Citations

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